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Title: SOP for rinsing the Nexera X2 Liquid Chromatograph (Shimadzu) prior to acquisition by Orbitrap Fusion (Thermo Scientific) mass spectrometer.

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Modules of Nexera X2 Liquid Chromatograph

Bottle tray holder, DGU-20A5R Degassing Unit, LC-30AD Liquid Chromatography Pump A and Pump B, SIL-30AC Autosampler, CTO-20AC Column Oven Prominence, CBM-20A Communication Bus Modul

Important

- Use UCL/MS grade absolute methanol and water (presently both from Biosolve Chimie SARL).
- Always use the corresponding precolumn to the column.
- Always adjust the needle stroke which differs for vials and well plates.

To turn ON the LC (optional for disabled LC)

1. Press the power switch (bottom left) to turn ON the LC modules in the following order: CBM, Pump A, Pump B, Autosampler and Column Oven, and wait until the LC stabilizes and connects to the MS.

Prior to chromatographic analysis - Be aware that to waste position (1-6) is applied by the MS tune SW

1. In the pump A and B module, check the vials and replace the current solution by the fresh one. Usually, 10 % methanol or 10 % isopropanol is used for flushing the pump pistons.
2. Replace the initial reservoir bottles with water and organic solvent for line A and B by those with mobile phase with water and organic solvent containing additives for line A and B, respectively.
3. For the pump A and B module:
 - a) Turn the drain valve knob 180° counterclockwise to open it, then press **purge** and let the LC purge up to twice in succession.
 - b) When purging is over, immediately turn clockwise the drain valve knob to close it.
4. In the front panel of the autosampler module (also check the Autosampler window setting, **Figure 1**):
 - a) Press **Rinse** for rinsing the needle by the rinse solution.
 - b) Press **Purge** to pumps rinse solution through flow lines, injection and rinsing port for specified time.

R₀ line (Rinse:R0) must be inserted into the same mobile phase as line A that is usually water containing additives which is used as initial concentration for gradient analysis.

R₁ and R₂ line (Rinse:R1 and Rinse:R2) serves rinsing by other solvents (e.g., methanol) or solvent mixtures.

R₃ line (Rinse:R3) heads to the closer rising port but this line is not configured to be used in the LC.
5. For the column oven module, unscrew the line tubing and replace the current adapter by the column with precolumn aligned with a flow direction.
6. Let the column with precolumn equilibrated for a certain period prior to chromatographic analysis.
7. Since the MS acquisition finish, follow this protocol using bottle reservoirs with water and organic solvent to remove mobile phase (water and organic solvent containing additives) from the precolumn with column and the line tubing of the LC.

To remove the buffer-containing mobile phase, flush the reserved phase column by

1. 10% of organic solvent (methanol) to avoid buffer precipitation
mobile phase A (90%, water) and mobile phase B (10%, organic solvent)
2. 50% of organic solvent (methanol)
mobile phase A (50%, water) and mobile phase B (50%, organic solvent)
3. 95% of organic solvent (methanol) to remove the column dirtiness
mobile phase A (5%, water) and mobile phase B (95%, organic solvent)

For each step, apply up to the half value of flowrate used for chromatographic analysis and flush the column by 50 times of its void volume. **To store the reserved phase column**, flush it by 80% of organic solvent (e.g., methanol) and keeps it in safe place.

Rinse and Purge is related with settings in the Shimadzu autosampler window (**Figure 1**)

Following the **rinse** pressing, the front panel of the autosampler shows:

- RINSING NDLE STD/DIP TIME: 15 sec; the needle is in the distant rinsing port.
- RINSING PORT R1/500 μ L, 1; the needle is in HPV injecting port and measuring pump delivers volume.

Following the **purge** pressing, the front panel of the autosampler shows:

- PURGING LINE R0/TIME LEFT 10.0
the needle is in the HPV injecting port and measuring pump purges measuring line by R0.
- PURGING PORT R2/TIME LEFT 10.0
the needle is in the HPV injecting port and measuring pump purges rinse port by R2.
- PURGING PORT R1/TIME LEFT 10.0
the needle is in the HPV injecting port and measuring pump purges rinse port by R1.

The screenshot displays the Shimadzu Autosampler software interface. The 'Rinse Type' is set to 'External/Internal'. The 'Rinse Settings' section includes: Rinse Speed (35 uL/sec), Rinse Port Liquid (R1), Rinsing Volume (500 uL), Rinse Mode (Before and after aspiration), and Rinse Dip Time (15 sec). The 'Rinse Pump' section shows Rinse Method (Rinse Port Only) and Rinse Time (2 sec). The 'Purge Settings' section shows Purge Time for Rinse Port (Purging with R1: 10.0 min, Purging with R2: 10.0 min) and Measuring Line (Purging with Default R0: 10.0 min). The 'Injection Settings' section includes Needle Stroke (52 mm), Control Vial Needle Stroke (52 mm), Sampling Speed (5.0 uL/sec), Cooler Temperature (15 °C), Measuring Line Purge Volume (600 uL), and Air Gap Volume (0.1 uL). The 'Use Autosampler' checkbox is checked. The 'Rack Type' is '1.5 mL Standard'. The 'SHIMADZU Solutions for Science' logo is visible at the bottom left, and 'Download' and 'Help' buttons are at the bottom right.

Figure 1 Software autosampler window shows the default values for External/Internal rinse type selection

APPENDIX

Sample Injection Process

- Mobile Phase (Mp) Flowline
Mp reservoir → HPV (high-pressure valve) → sample loop → needle → IP (injection port) → HPV → column
 - Release of Mobile Phase Flowline Pressure (HPV loading position)
needle → sample loop → HPV → LPV (low-pressure valve) → RP (rinsing port)
IP → HPV → drain
 - External Needle Rinsing before Sample Aspiration
IP/needle → RP/needle exterior dipping
 - Sample to Loop Aspiration
Sample vial → sample loop → HPV → LPV → MP (measuring pump)
 - External Needle Rinsing after Sample Aspiration
RP/needle exterior dipping → IP/needle
 - Sample Injection
IP/sample & mobile phase → HPV → column
 - Aspiration of Rinse Solution
bottle reservoir → LPV → MP
 - Dispensing Rinse Solution to Measuring Flowline
MP → LPV → HPV → drain
 - Dispensing Rinse Solution to Rinsing Port
MP → LPV → RP → drain
 - Internal Needle Rinsing with Rinse Solution
Mp reservoir → LPV → MP
MP → LPV → HPV → sample loop → needle interior → IP → HPV → drain
- IP rinsing becomes immediately after internal needle rinsing
IP/needle → RP/external needle rinsing → IP/needle raising & rinse solution dropping → IP/aspirating
the rinse-remaining component solution → RP/contaminated rinse solution discharge → IP/needle

Rinse Type and Settings: No Rinsing, External, External/Internal (recommended), Off (Fast LC)

- Rinsing speed: 1 – 35 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ in 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ step, (35 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ set); the flow rate of the needle rinsing.
- Rinse Port Liquid: R0, (R1 default), R2; the rinse solution type filling the rinse port.
- Rinsing Volume: 0 – 2000 μL in 1 μL step, (500 μL default); the volume used for rinse solution exchange in the rinse port and increase it for the evidence of cross-contamination.
- Rinse Mode: No rinsing, Before Aspiration, After Aspiration, Before and after Aspiration (recommended); the needle rinsing following the sample suction/injection.
- Rinse Dip Time: 0 – 60 sec in 1 sec step, (15 sec set); the time of needle dipping in the rinse port to clean the needle.
- Config Internal Rinse: sub-window shows further internal rinsing options.

Rinse Pump using the R3 line is not installed in this LC configuration.

Purge Settings

- Rinse Port: Purging with R1/R2: 0.1 – 25.0 min (10/10 mins set); purge time during rinse port purge.
- Measuring Line: Purging with Default R0: 0.1 – 25.0 (10 mins set); purge time during rinse port purge.
- Measuring Line Purge Volume: 600 μL is set automatically.

Rinse Solution Selection

- For R0, the mobile phase as initial concentration for the gradient analysis must be used.
- For reserved phase, ion exchange and aqueous normal phase use methanol/water (50%/50%, v/v).
- Do not use 1% or higher formic acid and acetic acid solution, 0.1% or higher TFA solution. Otherwise, volatile components may cause metals in the instrument to corrode.
- To prevent salt deposition, lower the organic solvent concentration to 50 % or less when using buffer exceeding concentration of 50 mmol.

The screenshot displays the Shimadzu LC software interface for configuring the instrument. The main window is titled "LC default_vial.meth - Thermo Xcalibur Instrument Setup". The interface is divided into several sections:

- Injection Settings:** Needle Stroke: 52 mm, Control Vial Needle Stroke: 52 mm, Sampling Speed: 5.0 uL/sec, Cooler Temperature: 15 °C, Measuring Line Purge Volume: 600 uL, Air Gap Volume: 0.1 uL.
- Rinse Settings:** Rinse Type: External/Internal, Rinsing Speed: 35 uL/sec, Rinse Port Liquid: R1, Rinsing Volume: 500 uL, Rinse Mode: Before and after aspiration, Rinse Dip Time: 0 sec.
- Rinse Pump:** Rinse Method: Rinse Port Only, Rinse Time: 2 sec.
- Purge Settings:** Rinse Port: Purging with R1 10.0 min, Purging with R2 10.0 min, Measuring Line: Purging with Default R0 10.0 min.
- Internal Rinse:** A diagram shows the internal rinse process with three stages: (1) Rinsing Start Time, (2) Equilibration Start Time, and (3) Equilibration Hold Time. The diagram also shows the status of the High Pressure Valve (LOAD, INJ, LOAD, INJ) and the Analytical Time (min) axis.
- Internal Rinse Settings:** (1) Rinsing Start Time: 1.000000 min, Rinsing Sequence: R0 -> R0 -> R1 -> R1, Rinsing Volume R0 R1 R2: 300 uL, Injection Port Rinsing: R0, R1, R2 checked, Expected End Time: 5.5 min.

Figure 2 shows default External/Internal rinse type in a detail for the selected method

Note: The used figures were obtained from the Shimadzu software controlling the LC instrument.